

The Experience of Desire from the *Roman de la Rose* to *Reason and Sensuallyte*

Many of you here have already pointed to the seminal role of the *Roman de la Rose* in inaugurating a 'new wave' of self-consciously intellectual, and perhaps philosophical vernacular poetry in the later Middle Ages, and my paper today looks at this legacy.

In my recent work I have been arguing the *Rose* uses first-person dream poetry as a kind of open-ended workshop for intellectual speculation in narrative form. This is possible because the 'I' of the protagonist is 'open' and unspecific, and becomes a space of projection for the subjectivity of its reader, who can **think and feel and imagine** themselves into the fiction, 'inhabiting' the many philosophical problems that are raised (but not resolved) by the poem.

Dream vision poetry therefore functions as an extended and open-ended thought experiments in narrative form, and I have insisted on the intellectually enabling, heuristic, and perhaps even 'experimental' nature of this kind of allegorical narrative.

But ... I am also beginning to wonder whether claim isn't a little too optimistic and in its own way rather too 'positivistic', and whether it should be slightly inflected and nuanced. And I say this because (1) many of the poets active in this genre rather worry about the moral legitimacy and epistemic status and reliability of this sort of poetic 'makynge' - Langland, Deguileville, Chaucer, and of course Jean Gerson and Christine de Pizan... all in different ways; but also (2) because many later texts in this tradition seem far less adventurous in their use of the form, and often use dream vision allegory less to facilitate intellectual speculation, but perhaps to constrain that very speculation, to regulate and channel it into a very specific direction.

This is a much bigger conversation, and I don't want to generalise, or extrapolate too many 'grand narratives' from anecdotal evidence. But the case study I want to focus on today seems to suggest something of this kind...

So, the texts: my main object is the Middle English *Reason & Sensuallyte*, about 1410, often attributed to Lydgate although the attribution is disputed by some. This poem is a translation of a French source that already looks back to the RR - the French *Eschez amoureux*, dated to 1370s. Because we have 3 stages, it becomes possible to trace some sort of progression, that in my opinion describes this movement **away** from the radical experimental possibilities opened up by the *Rose*. In particular, this traces a movement away from I call the 'experientialist bias' of the RR. So, for avoidance of doubt, my reading of the RR sees it very much as a poem that affirms the centrality of experience while interrogating (and eroding) the

weight of *auctoritee* or *auctoritas* - I've included the one passage that to my mind makes this point rather forcefully... quote 1

Let me first provide a very rough summary of the EA, before comparing the French source with its English translation.

The *acteur* is in a typical spring setting, and encounters dame Nature, quote 2 who presents him with the choice of two paths, each of them associated with a specific form of knowledge: the path of **Reason & Understandinge**, which assimilates man with the divine; and the path of **vertu sensityf** - essentially knowledge relying on the input from the external senses. He moves on and, encounters three goddesses Venus, Juno, or Pallas, and he has to essentially repeat the Judgment of Paris; of course he goes for Venus... He then meets Diana, who chastises him for his bad choice. He persists in his loyalty to Venus, and eventually arrives in the Garden of Déduit, and he observes how the Garden corresponds exactly to the details found in the earlier description of this place in the RR quote 3: *Oiseuse, the God of love with his arrows, the fountain of Narcissus, etc.* The *acteur* now witnesses a game of Chess between a Lady and Deduis, which the Lady wins. It is now the turn of the *acteur* to play against the lady; the chess-pieces are now described, and allegorised, but this however is where the English translation breaks off, before the match can begin . 5 MINS We are only 5000 lines into the poem (over 30'000 *vers*...), but the remainder of EA can be summarised pretty quickly: the *acteur* eventually loses his game; he pays homage to the God of Love; is given a thorough instruction in the art of Love by Cupid; Cupid departs, and Pallas arrives on the scene. Predictably, Pallas talks up the excellence of the contemplative life, which she embodies - at the expense of the active life (Juno), and the voluptuous life (Venus). Strikingly, however, Pallas's long lecture (over 15'000 verses..) also contains a wealth of useful practical instruction about governance, family management, and the active life in the secular sphere more generally,... and in fact her lecture draws extensively on Giles of Rome's *de Regimine Principum*.

So, while it is fair to say that EA is a poem that, like many others, is grounded in a broadly moralised reading of the RR (condemning voluptuous living and analysing the dangers of erotic infatuation..), it can't really be said that the French poem dismisses any secular values and the active life altogether. *Vita activa is, up to a point, a legitimate form of living.. even if it falls short of the perfections of vita contemplativa.* This makes for an interesting, complex, nuanced, and perhaps not entirely coherent ideological project for this poem...

RS clearly inherits the broadly moral slant of the original EA, but arguably sharpens any condemnation of eroticism. I'd love to exemplify this - and have a mass of 'evidence' - but there just isn't enough time...

What I am really interested in, however, is that the two poems represent the **experience of erotic desire** in subtly different ways, assigning very different value and significance to this experience. To be more exact, I would like to examine the two poems in terms of their handling of the competing claims of *experience* and *auctoritee*.... *experientia* and *auctoritas*. This tension, while not entirely absent from the French poem, becomes a real concern in the English translation... which (unlike its source) comes down rather firmly on the side of *auctoritas* and against experience...

I want to start by identifying some very broad changes made in the translation, before focusing on its discussion of experience very specifically.

- Firstly, the English RS contains a wealth of references to its source. 'as myn auctor tellys' RS 933; 'as seyth my boke' RS 1030; ' the booke seyth thus' RS 1035. This highlights the English poem's status as a translation, and reminds us that the poem's narrator/translator is NOT, or no longer, identical with the fictional *acteur*... This places the visionary experience at one remove from the poet, and at two removes from the reader, emphasising the 'literariness' and literary genealogy of the English poem...
- Second, there are also a wealth of general references to unspecified writings of other clerks, poets, and *auctores*: 'as clerkes wryte / And in her bookes lyst endyte ' RS 1037-8; 'Rede poetys and ye shal se' RS 1051; 'As poetys specyfy' RS 1612; 'poetis pleynly write thus' RS 1645; 'olde poetys writen so' RS 1755. None of this is in the source, and again, this lends the whole poem a greater sense of 'bookishness': we realise that we are not so much reading the account of 'raw' lived personal experience, but that such an experience has been collated against a wealth of learned sources, particularly mythographic, encyclopaedic, and exemplary ones. It is these sources, these other books, that, as it were, lend 'meaning' (*senefiance*) to the actual events...
- Which brings me to my next, third point... On the whole, the translation is far more 'exegetical' or 'explicative' than the original. It is didactic and exemplaristic where the original is more descriptive, leisurely, and allusive... The translator often takes on the task of unpacking the *senefiance* of various exemplary narratives at some length in the main text, and no longer relies only on Latin marginalia to achieve this (as was the case in the original). Also, the poem now includes some direct appeals to the reader by the narrator - again something that we do not find in the original...where this kind of 'lecturing' only happens between the fictional characters (Nature, Pallas, Diana) and the hapless *acteur* — and this instructional dimension is again considerably expanded in the translation.

10 MINS

Despite this increased emphasis on the importance of allegorical exposition in RS, the *acteur* - just like *Amant* in the RR - shown little interest in the 'integumentum aus poetes' and remains a stubbornly literal reader. In QUOTE 4 he says 'I have no intention of seeking out the Golden Fleece like Jason, or to fly across the sea like Icarus...' and in the process completely misses the *moralitee* of these tales, used by Diana to try and dissuade him from following Venus...

I'm particularly interested in what happens next in this passage — especially in the English translation, which considerably intensifies the idea: the reason the *acteur* has no interest in such moral exempla is that he is far too interested in natural phenomena - and Kellie has explored the underlying discomfort with *Scientia Naturalis* that pervades the English poem in her book, a reading that dovetails very nicely with my own...

QUOTE 4:

Not only is this more insistent, but it invites readers to put a more clearly negative spin on the *acteur's curiositas* - I'm rather struck by the statement that "reson out I wolde fynde / After the course oonly of kynde". This to me implies a rather mechanistic or 'physicalistic' kind of naturalism that we are meant to disapprove of. The implication is that it is not through 'empirical experience', but through moral and allegorical exposition that we obtain valuable, and especially *viable* knowledge.

COGNITION (internal senses)

This newly intensified epistemological concern with the relative value of different types of knowledge also produces a more extended discussion of mental processes, about the mechanics of perception, cognition, deliberation/judgement/assent. And much of this points to an exacerbated anxiety about erroneous judgement, especially when the latter is primarily determined by sensory input. You could say - perhaps - that the poem identifies the dangers of a passive, physicalistic and deterministic model of cognition, where the mind is literally 'inscribed' or 'imprinted' by sensory experiences (*this roughly corresponds to the stoic theory of cognition as outlined in Boethius' Consolation of Philosophy Bk V, m4*). And it is precisely this semantic field of 'imprinting' that is used in the translation to warn us against the dangers of *vertu sensityf* - a semantic field that is entirely absent from the source/

So, prudent Women are identified as those who are able to resist the 'imprinting' of 'sugared words' in their hearts (in a passage that is added wholesale to the source): both QUOTE 5

A further passage (also original in the translation) is less optimistic about female resistance to 'imprinting' of this kind, and again uses the same vocabulary **QUOTE 5** again:

*An interesting occurrence was already cited, as part of the *acteur's* speech where he refuses to engage in the kind of allegorical reading recommended by Diana, and reaffirms instead his desire to seek knowledge about natural phenomena **QUOTE 4**. There, at the very end of the passage, he mentions that*

***I ha this effeccion
Prentyd in myn oppinion,
RS 4611-23***

The idea here is perhaps less directly about the mind being determined by sensory 'impression', and more about a mental fixation: the determination to seek knowledge about natural phenomena is indelibly imprinted, or 'set' in his mind, determining his belief (opinio)

15 MINS

In all three cases this form of imprinting has clearly negative associations, the implication being that it ought to be resisted or avoided altogether.

But there are some positive counterexamples: the idea is that the mind can be advantageously shaped, and literally 'informed', but this time not by sensory input but rather by means of moral teachings conveyed through verbal or textual instruction. Take this example in the description of the arms of Pallas, where the reader (and not the *acteur*) is told by the translator to **emprynte in your memorye** the allegorical exposition he is about to provide **QUOTE 6**:

Now because there are both positive and negative forms of imprinting, the mind requires careful policing and a solid second-order response. Take this other example, it is the opening speech by Diana, who points out to the *acteur* that he has been duped by Venus, and should reconsider his choice, based on erroneous judgement. **QUOTE 7**: The instructional tone and the reference to the internal senses and imaginative faculty is not entirely absent from EA, but the English version really lays it on pretty thick, and makes a rather different point. There is a lot of rather anxious emphasis, it seems to me, about the cognitive and deliberative processes involved in forming opinion and producing assent, and the point really is that the *acteur* should trust not sensory impression but rather the words of Diana (who is trying to 'enfourmen' the *acteur* by 'preching' to him). The point of the French; by contrast, is much more along the lines of: 'you're not going to listen to me anyway... so just go ahead and you will find out for yourself that I was right'...

In general, then, it seems that forms of imprinting based on sensory input are generally negative, while 'good' imprinting generally has its origins in some verbal lesson and moral instruction.

*Cut here if no time... Skip QUOTES 8-10 All in all, then, RS is pervaded by an underlying sense of anxiety about the **deceptiveness of appearances** (RS 2250, 3169, 3206)— something the EA is much more sanguine about, and does not identify as a major theme.*

Take this passage, the end of Mercury's extended speech about the three Goddesses (Pallas June and Venus) and the acteur's need to make his choice **QUOTE 8**:

The English translation is full of rather agonised technical description of the decision-making process — and there really is none of this in the original French: there is a simple question. I also find it rather amusing how the passage he simultaneously emphasises the acteur's free will ('thou hauest lyberte', and yet simultaneously reminds him that such 'lyberte' ought to be informed 'by counsayl and rede of me'; again, the emphasis is on verbal instruction and mental deliberation - not on sensory input and perception...

*The most striking example for this perhaps occurs when the Goddess Diana seeks to reveal to the acteur that his choice of Venus is based precisely on the erroneous assumption that her pleasing aspect denotes a positive, virtuous moral disposition - again turning what is a passing comment in EA into a laborious scrutiny of epistemic processes **QUOTE 9**:*

Comment on 'repenting'... as 'make amends', 'make penitence', 'relinquish'...

*The question of the disjunction between sensory experience and internal 'doom' or judgement (or 'assent', to use the technical term..) is developed throughout the exchange that follows. Where the acteur in EA simply states that on the basis of experience to date there is nothing untoward to report about Venus (*je n' ay encore trouvé, De tant que j' en ay esprouvé, Fors que tout bien*), RS again develops at length and more technically **QUOTE 10**:*

*Clearly the passage in the translation goes out of its way to underline the problematic epistemic status of 'proof' and 'experience', and in fact points to the **insufficiency of experience** unaided by some form of higher guidance and correction - which is readily provided, of course, by Diana, and (implicitly) by the poet, with his tendency to inflate any expository, interpretive, and didactic impetus that is often merely implicit in the text of the EA or in its marginal Latin glosses. Notice also how insistently Diana emphasises the crucial role of instruction in her opening couplet: "My faire frende, yif thou lyst **lere**, / Somwhat of Venus thou shalt **here**" here the rhyme*

'Iere/here' really visualises the idea that knowledge is inextricably tied up with 'hearing and listening' to moral instruction rather than simply relying on the supposed 'proof' derived from sensory experience and — all too readily misconstrued in the 'fantasy' of the perceiver / acteur...

It is symptomatic therefore that RS (unlike EA) is constantly preoccupied with drawing our attention to the unstable and uncertain nature of 'opinion' - a term that is used 13 times in RS (e.g. also 5983), and only once in the corresponding section of EA. RS is therefore not only more interested in epistemological matters, but also far more anxious, and perhaps 'sceptical' about the processing of sensory information in the mind and the formation of judgements...

Short to here is no time... All in all, then, RS is pervaded by an underlying sense of anxiety about the **deceptiveness of appearances** (RS 2250, 3169, 3206)— something the EA is much more sanguine about, and does not identify as a major theme.

EXPERIENCE

So far everything I've been saying suggests that in comparison to its source, RS is a poem that is far from comfortable with the idea of empirical, sensory 'experience' in general. This does not mean that the vocabulary of experience disappears from the translation - on the contrary; if anything, this concern with experience is more, not less prominent in the translation.

The reason for this is not only that RS works so hard to disqualify or discredit the value of 'experience', but it also effectively **transforms and redefines** the meaning of 'experience' altogether.

Let me illustrate how this happens and then I'll wrap up

This is a short snippet from the speech given by the God Mercury as he prepares to restage the judgement of Paris. Quite apart from the shift from the fairly neutral and descriptive tone of EA to the more sententious and schoolmasterly tone of RS, the English translation also introduces the idea of proof or 'euydence'

QUOTE 11:

But such 'euydence' is not at all provided by empirical testing or sensory experience of some sort, but by means of verbal exposition: **I shal yive the euydence, First expovne... Of alle the mater, how hit stood**

20 MINS

Another revealing discussion of experience in this sense, perhaps, is the following. This comes from the condemnation of Venus contained in Diana's speech:

QUOTE 12

The point is: Experience will teach you that Venus is like the monstrous *Chimera*. You can see that the mention of the Chimera is already there in the source, but RS introduces the idea that this figure provides the reader with 'experience' of the dangers of eros. But what exactly does our 'experience' of a chimera teach us, or what does it even look or feel like? There is, I find, a rather delightful unintentional irony in the fact that the poet invokes an entirely phantastic, imaginary animal that simply is not actually available as the object of direct empirical 'experience'.

Something very similar happens with another mythical beast, the Siren RS 3641-54, and with the description of 'serpentys and dragouns', all of them supposedly found in the Garden of Cupid: "**And who abytt ther eny while, / He shal haue experyence / Of ther cruel violence**" (RS 3910-13).

Rather than understanding experience as we would, as a form of 'empirical' experience mediated by the senses, then, experience in RS often comes to mean something else. Here experience describes at best what might be produced by a thought experiment, relying on the formation of an opinion or idea on the basis of a mental image that has no physical substance at all... and that exists (significantly) only in books, and not in reality. More generally, then, the English poem associates proof not so much with empirical experience, but with various forms of textual or literary 'evidence' that is used to visualise a moral lesson: '**Examples preve** it more than oon', RS 4161 says Diana (the source uses neither proof nor exemplum... *EA 3241-3*).

To sum up my points so far: RS makes a distinct effort to foreground the importance of instruction, literary tradition, exemplary narratives, and carefully constructed mental images with an allegorical meaning **at the expense of** actual experience.

BUT there's a snag - and it's a big one... the problem is that this logic runs contrary to the spirit of the original French poem. In fact, the whole poem is really predicated on the injunction to the acteur, pronounced by Nature herself, that he should go out into the world and seek knowledge — and more specifically self-knowledge. **QUOTE 13:**

Interestingly, the English translation replaces this incentive to self-knowledge (*De ta grant dignité congnoistre, / Et que tu le puissez accroistre*) with a rather more pedestrian, normative moral advice 'fro vycis to restraine' (the incentive is didactic rather than exploratory...)

This injunction to 'go out and see the world' is later picked up by the acteur, to counter Diana's advice that he should take up the life of a hermit: **QUOTE 14:**

The differences again are subtle but striking: in EA the emphasis falls in equal measure on the sensory appeal and on the desire for scientific knowledge of natural phenomena: '**la beaulté**' but also '**cognoistre**' - and the implication is that both pleasure and scientific knowledge are, up to a point, legitimate, 'natural' pursuits... In RS, by contrast, the description is almost exclusively focused on the sensory or sensual appeal of nature, subtly nudging the reader to buy into the moralising disapproval of this kind of harmful, illegitimate curiosity. Notice also the emphasis on '*attendaunce*' - attention - which again brings the idea of judgement and deliberate assent into the picture (a notion absent from EA). And of course the use of '**privetee**' here is very much, I suggest, loaded with deliberate Chaucerian echoes, and has been chosen to highlight the intellectual hybris that feeds what is not merely *vana curiositas* but a form of transgressive (and implicitly lascivious) desire for knowledge of natural phenomena.

But to return to my main point: there is a tension here between the fact that the poem we start with (the EA) that values experience, and embraces the idea that one should seek practical, empirical confirmation of traditional teaching in practice. This idea is to some extent hard-wired into the narrative, flowing from Nature's initial injunction to go out into the world and seek such knowledge (of whatever kind..). But RS - a poem that by necessity inherits this narrative direction - is a poem that in many ways seeks to evade direct experience.

So, the tension here is that in some sense RS is trying to suppress the quite pronounced experiential bias that is hard-wired into its source, the EA, and which ultimately goes back to the RR. Now as we've seen the EA is a poem that clearly presupposes the reader's familiarity with the *Rose*, and in fact presents itself as a response or rewriting of JdM's poem. But on closer inspection things are actually more interesting, because the *acteur* not only finds himself in an imaginary landscape that is reminiscent of the RR, but **recognises** this fact. In short, he observes that his experiences **reproduce** and thus **confirm** the validity of the descriptions contained the earlier poem (**quote 3**):

Nothing special perhaps, as many other poems feature dreams that implicitly or explicitly echo the experience of reading the '*biau Roman de la Rose*' (Chaucer's *Book of the Duchess*...). But what happens in the EA (and the RS) is rather different, because we are NOT in fact in a dream at all...

The EA in fact is an account of a waking vision - and this is a point that is made clearly and insistently at the start of the poem **quote 15**:

The point here is that this is a waking vision, perhaps in the manner of Boethius's *Consolation* - an idea that is picked up again in the *Commentary to the EA*, the EAM, authored by Evrart de Conty **quote 16**:

Nous avons donc quant a ce premier point .iii. manieres de faindre: l' une par revelacion d' un mort resuscité, l' autre par maniere de songe et **l' autre par ymaginaire vision. Et par ceste tierce maniere parle l' aucteur** du livre rimé dessusdit dont nous voulons parler, quant il faint que Nature se vint a moustrer a ly, **par quoy il vould pretendre que ceste vision reele qui des yeulx corporeulx se feist a la lectre ainz fut tant seulement ymaginee telle.**¹

I take this to mean - as do the editors of the poem - that the narrative of the EA has a higher truth-value than the Dream Vision of the RR. In fact, I would like to suggest that the EA very deliberately presents the adventures of its own *acteur* as a sort of testing and validation of the veracity of the reported dream that makes up the earlier poem by GdL and JdM.

And indeed, the *acteur* makes it very clear that he is not going to be satisfied with anyone's reported account of what happens in the *Jardin de Deduit*, and is determined to find out for himself whether the account he finds in the poetic tradition is truthful **quote 17**:

The translator's discomfort with this emphasis on the value of experience idea is reflected not only in the small-scale changes I have reviewed, but also in the poem's larger conceptual structure. Now, remember that the poem starts out as a waking vision and not as a dream, in both versions, with all the implications I have just explored... BUT... the English translation very quickly, and almost imperceptibly slides back into the more conventional mode of the dream. This becomes clear in two passages: **quote 18**:

It seems the translator has now changed his mind... and we are not - or no longer - reading an account of a first-person protagonist's ostensibly real-life waking experience.... Rather (just as in Chaucer's *Book of the Duchess*) we are reading the account of a dream that reproduces the events of an anterior literary dream....

This move - and it strikes me as a highly deliberate choice, especially in the second extract - has again a distancing, defamiliarising effect upon the reader. Of course we can still think ourselves into the fiction... but we are aware that it is already **imagined and not experienced** by the *acteur* (who in any case is NOT identical

¹ Evrart de Conty, *EAM*, 9^v44-10^r2, p.24.

with the English translator who repeatedly reminds us that he is transcribing the book of 'myn auctour... who sayth thus'). And we suddenly find ourselves at two removes from the action (or is it three?). It is in the truest sense a thought experiment - not an experience we are invited to reproduce in our own real waking lives. The subtext is: stay away from the Garden of Deduit...no point in looking further, because this book here tells you all you need to know about it.

If this is true, then the two poems are actually making a very different point about experience and auctoritee despite their extremely close similarities:

> The EA seems to be telling us that no amount of poetic description of the realities of erotic desire can replace the experience itself. Yes, of course there is already a vast available archive of wisdom and moral instruction to tell us about the dangers of erotic desire... But no matter how truthful and persuasive this might all be, each individual is eventually bound to seek out a personal experience of desire - even if only to validate such pre-existing truth and wisdom. Any existing accounts and descriptions of erotic desire preserved in the collective literary archive can only ever function as gloss or blueprint for an individual, lived personal experience, whose details and felt intensity are unique even if they loosely conform to a pattern. *Experience* and *auctoritee* are complementary, they go hand in hand, 'contreres choses, les unes des autres gloses'.

> RS, however, explodes this dialecticism between experience and auctoritee. The translation invites us to distance ourselves from this protagonist - who really is reduced to the exemplary embodiment of a 'fol amoureux', as is the case in many other moralised responses to the RR. Now that the events are being put back 'inside the box' of a dream, as it were, they are more easily kept at a distance. We are witnessing an exemplary tale of perdition, and rather than being invited to experience such truths for ourselves, and perhaps compare notes, we are simply invited to observe and especially to *listen*. It is as though the *acteur* is having, or rather dreaming up, conjuring up this fictional experience of desire **for us..**, on our behalf... so we don't have to. All that is left for us to do, is to sit back and perform the work of allegorical interpretation and moralisation that the *acteur* himself refuses to, or is unable to, take on.

This is hardly evidence for the continuing 'rise' of an experiential poetics in late medieval England (as I perhaps foolishly assumed when I started this project...). Rather than functioning as a script that could help us to gloss and understand the experiences that Nature invites us to pursue in the outside world, R&S proposes itself as a **surrogate** for an experience we should seek to avoid altogether.